

Restricted ideal pseudo-intuitionistic sets

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Abstract: In this article we introduce restricted (and unrestricted) ideal pseudo-intuitionistic sets. In this way, we continue our earlier line of research. The idea is to generalize Çoker's intuitionistic sets and to combine them with weak rough sets. We obtain a new class of objects that has certain connections with neutrosophic crisp and picture sets (but is more flexible). We define and study several logical operators and we prove various algebraic properties of them.

Key words: ideal pseudo-intuitionistic sets, intuitionistic sets, weak rough sets

1. Introductory notes

In modern logic, set theory and topology we have many classes of so-called *non-classical sets*. Basically, they are used to model various aspects of non-probabilistic uncertainty. Perhaps the most known are *fuzzy sets* introduced by Zadeh in [18]. As we know, the idea is that instead of the characteristic function of a set we use an interval $[0, 1]$. Atanassov (see [2]) extended this project. In his opinion, it is good to use two functions: one to model the level of membership and the second one to deal with non-membership. However, their values sum up to not more than 1, hence there is a kind of dependence between them. Thus, Smarandache introduced *neutrosophic sets* (see [13]) where we have three components (belonging, non-belonging and indifference). Each of them can take any value in $[0, 1]$, hence they can even sum up to 3. In fact, $3 - T(x) - F(x) - I(x)$ can be considered as the fourth logical value: the true indeterminacy. For example, in [12] neutrosophic minimal structures are discussed.

There are many other concepts of this kind. Among them there are those that are crisp (but still non-classical). In particular, we mean Çoker's *intuitionistic sets* (see [4], [5], [8]). Each intuitionistic set consists of two separate parts: accepted (true) elements of universe and rejected (false) elements. However, there are also those objects that are beyond these two sets. They are neutral. Çoker's sets are like crisp version of intuitionistic fuzzy sets. In the same way, *neutrosophic crisp sets* (see [10]) are crisp version of neutrosophic sets. Picture sets (see [6]) are an example of neutrosophic crisp sets. Their further investigation is presented in [7].

Moreover, we have *double sets* (see [14]), known as *weak rough sets* too (see [15]). Each set of this kind is nested: the subset of necessary elements is contained in the subset of possible elements. In fact, double sets are isomorphic with Çoker's sets and with our *possible paraconsistent sets* (introduced in [17]).

We have *triple sets* (see [16]) that combine intuitionistic sets with double sets. They are known as NCT-sets too (see [1]). Another amalgam of these two classes was presented in [3] under the name of *interval-valued*

intuitionistic sets. Similar approach is visible in [9].

Fuzzy sets are combined with the idea of multi-sets too. One of the newest examples (in the context of topology) is presented in [11].

In this paper we combine intuitionistic sets with weak rough sets (but in a different manner than in previous works of other authors). There are two innovations. First, we assume that the intersection of two components (representing truth and falsity) is not necessarily empty. Rather, the idea is that it belongs to some ideal on X . This is because Çoker's definition of algebraic operators can be easily adapted to this approach. Thus, a kind of "internal paraconsistency" is accepted in our setting. Second, both truth and falsity component are contained in a kind of "relativized universe" or "sub-universe". Thus, the process (or the act) of evaluation of the elements of X is somewhat "restricted".

2. General notions

Let us recall the very notion of ideal. The definition presented below is typical for set theory and topology.

Definition 2.1. Let X be a non-empty universe. An *ideal* \mathcal{I} on X is any non-empty family of subsets of X satisfying the following two conditions:

1. If $B \in \mathcal{I}$ and $A \subseteq B$, then $A \in \mathcal{I}$ (closure under subsets).
2. If $A, B \in \mathcal{I}$, then $A \cup B \in \mathcal{I}$.

If $X \notin \mathcal{I}$, then we say that \mathcal{I} is *proper*. Clearly, this means that $\mathcal{I} \neq P(X)$.

Remark 2.1. Note that the first condition stated in Def. 2.1 implies that $\emptyset \in \mathcal{I}$ (for each \mathcal{I}). This is because empty set is contained in every classical set. In particular, $\{\emptyset\}$ is an ideal too.

Moreover, it is visible that every ideal is closed under intersections. This property is a direct consequence of closure under subsets: suppose that both A and B belong to \mathcal{I} . Then $A \cap B$ is a subset of A (or B , it does not matter), hence $A \cap B \in \mathcal{I}$. In fact, this is true even for arbitrary (in particular, infinite) families too.

3. Elementary notions of our theory

In this section we sketch our general framework. We define the objects that we shall be dealing with throughout the paper. Moreover, we introduce basic algebraic operations. Basically, they are counterparts of classical union and intersection. However, our framework allows us to define more specific and less typical connectives too.

Definition 3.1. Suppose that X is a non-empty universe. Let \mathcal{I} be an ideal on X . Assume that A_T , A_F and X_A are three subsets of X such that $A_T \cup A_F \subseteq X_A$ and $A_T \cap A_F \in \mathcal{I}$. Then we shall say that an ordered triple $A = (A_T, A_F, X_A)$ is a *restricted ideal pseudo-intuitionistic set* on X . For brevity, we can say that A is a *RIP-I set* on X . The set of all RIP-I sets on X will be denoted as $\mathfrak{P}_{RI}(X)$.

What is the justification of this definition? First, we can say that X_A is a *relativized universe* of A . It means that while X contains all those objects that are "visible" or "reachable", X_A gathers only those that are "investigated" (e.g. by a decision maker whose viewpoint is described by means of A). As for the elements in A_T , they are "true" or "accepted", while those in A_F are evaluated as "false" and thus "rejected". However, it is possible that $A_T \cap A_F \neq \emptyset$. It contains those elements that are somewhat "paraconsistent" or "uncertain".

In the next definition we single out several subclasses of RIP-I sets.

Definition 3.2. Suppose that X is a non-empty universe and \mathcal{I} is an ideal on X . Let $A = (A_T, A_F, X_A)$ be a RIP-I set on X . We say that A is:

1. *Unrestricted ideal pseudo-intuitionistic* (that is, *UIP-I*) set if $X_A = X$.
2. *Restricted pseudo-intuitionistic* (that is, *RP-I*) set if $A_T \cap A_F = \emptyset$.
3. *Pseudo-intuitionistic* (that is, *P-I*) set if $X_A = X$ and $A_T \cap A_F = \emptyset$.

Clearly, pseudo-intuitionistic sets are just intuitionistic sets in the sense of Çoker. As for the restricted pseudo-intuitionistic sets, they can be considered as a subclass of picture sets. Finally, picture sets are a special case of neutrosophic crisp sets. Note, however, that our approach is more general than the neutrosophic crisp one. This is because we engage ideals. Thus, we accept non-empty intersection of A_T and A_F . Hence, we divide the whole space into five (not just four) mutually disjoint parts.

As for the picture sets, note that every picture set can be viewed as an RP-I set. If $P = (P_1, P_2, P_3)$ is a picture set, then we can say that $A = (A_T, A_F, X_A)$ is an RP-I set where $A_T = P_1$, $A_F = P_3$ and $X_A = (P_1 \cup P_2 \cup P_3)$.

Other interpretations and viewpoints are possible too. Recall that triple sets (as presented in [16]) combine two concepts in one package. First, each triple set is a pair of mutually disjoint classical sets. This approach resembles Çoker's idea of intuitionistic sets. Second, one of these classical sets has a structure of weak rough set: it consists of the internal part that is contained in the external one.

Now let us compare this with restricted pseudo-intuitionistic sets. First, they have a structure of weak rough set: the internal part $A_T \cup A_F$ is contained in the external one (that is, in X_A). Second, A_T and A_F form an intuitionistic set because their intersection is empty. In the most general version, it is not necessarily empty but belongs to the ideal \mathcal{I} .

Remark 3.1. Note that if we have non-empty universe X and A is an RP-I set on X , then it induces several triple sets. For example, these are:

1. $T = (T_1, T_2, T_3)$, where $T_1 = A_T$, $T_2 = X_A \setminus A_F$, $T_3 = A_F$.
2. $S = (S_1, S_2, S_3)$, where $S_1 = A_T$, $S_2 = X_A \setminus A_F$, $S_3 = X \setminus X_A$.
3. $U = (U_1, U_2, U_3)$, where $U_1 = A_T$, $U_2 = X_A \setminus A_F$, $U_3 = (X \setminus X_A) \cup A_F$.

Clearly, triple sets can introduce RP-I sets too. For example, assume that $T = (T_1, T_2, T_3)$ is a triple set. Hence, $T_1 \subseteq T_2$ and $T_2 \cup T_3 = \emptyset$. Then $A = (A_T, A_F, X_A)$ is an RP-I set if $A_T = T_1$, $A_F = T_3$ and $X_A = T_2 \cup T_3$.

Now let us introduce basic algebraic operations on RIP-I sets. We shall see that both our generalizations (the one based on ideals and the one based on relative universes) are very natural. The operations that are known from the theory of Çoker's set can be easily extended to our framework.

Definition 3.3. Let X be a non-empty universe and assume that \mathcal{I} is an ideal on X . Suppose that A and B are two RIP-I sets on X . Then we define their:

1. *(Standard) Intersection* as $C = A \cap B = (A_T \cap B_T, A_F \cup B_F, X_A \cup X_B)$.
2. *(Standard) Union* as $C = A \cup B = (A_T \cup B_T, A_F \cap B_F, X_A \cup X_B)$.

3. *Strong intersection* as $C = A \wedge B = (A_T \cap B_T, A_F \cap B_F, X_A \cup X_B)$.
4. *Strict intersection* as $C = A \Delta B = (A_T \cap B_T, A_F \cap B_F, X_A \cap X_B)$.

The crucial thing is to prove that all these operations produce new RIP-I sets. This is the content of the lemma below.

Lemma 3.1. *Suppose that X is a non-empty universe with an ideal \mathcal{I} on it. Suppose that A and B are RIP-I sets on X . Then $A \cap B$, $A \cup B$, $A \wedge B$ and $A \Delta B$ are RIP-I sets too.*

Proof. Let us consider each case:

1. As for the standard intersection, we have $A \cap B = (A_T \cap B_T, A_F \cup B_F, X_A \cup X_B)$. Obviously, $(A_T \cap B_T) \cup (A_F \cup B_F) \subseteq X_A \cup X_B$. Now, according to classical distributivity laws, we have $(A_T \cap B_T) \cap (A_F \cup B_F) = (A_T \cap B_T \cap A_F) \cup (A_T \cap B_T \cap B_F)$. By the very definition of RIP-I sets, $A_T \cap A_F \in \mathcal{I}$. Clearly, $A_T \cap B_T \cap A_F \subseteq A_T \cap A_F$, so $A_T \cap B_T \cap A_F \in \mathcal{I}$. In a similar manner we can prove that $A_T \cap B_T \cap B_F \in \mathcal{I}$. But then the union of these two sets belongs to \mathcal{I} too.
2. This is similar to the intersection case.
3. As for the strong intersection, we can say that, obviously, $(A_T \cap B_T) \cup (A_F \cap B_F) \subseteq X_A \cup X_B$. Then we have $(A_T \cap B_T) \cap (A_F \cap B_F) = (A_T \cap A_F) \cap (B_T \cap B_F)$. Clearly, both components of this intersection belong to \mathcal{I} , so their intersection is in \mathcal{I} too. Note that in case of this particular operator it would be sufficient to assume that \mathcal{I} is a family closed under (finite) intersections.
4. Similar to the strong intersection case. Note that $(A_T \cap B_T) \cup (A_F \cap B_F) \subseteq X_A \cap X_B$.

□

Remark 3.2. *We proved that our algebra is closed under the operations defined above. Note that this property is true for any ideal on X . On the other hand, it is clear that if we change the ideal, we change the set of RIP-I sets too.*

Remark 3.3. *One could ask: is it possible to define "strong union" in an appropriate manner? Perhaps the easiest way is to use the following definition: that for any two RIP-I sets on X their strong union (with respect to some ideal \mathcal{I}) is $C = A \vee B = (A_T \cup B_T, (A_F \cup B_F) \setminus (A_T \cup B_T), X_A \cup X_B)$.*

Note, however, that this definition is somewhat specific. We see that $C_T \cap C_F$ belongs to \mathcal{I} just because this intersection is empty (and empty set belongs to any ideal). Hence, this operation always produce RP-I sets.

Let us go back to the core of our considerations. It seems that this is a good moment to introduce some notion of negation.

Definition 3.4. Let X be a non-empty universe with an ideal \mathcal{I} . If $A = (A_T, A_F, X_A)$ is an RIP-I set on X then we identify its *complement* with $A^c = (A_F, A_T, X_A)$. Obviously, A^c is an RIP-I set for every A .

Also, four distinguished types of sets should be introduced.

Definition 3.5. Let X be a non-empty universe. Then we define RIP-I:

1. *Universal set* as $\hat{X} = (X, \emptyset, X)$. It means that all elements of universe are evaluated and then all of them are accepted (considered true). None are rejected (that is, considered false).

2. *Empty set* as $\hat{\emptyset} = (\emptyset, X, X)$. Again, all the elements are evaluated. But now they are all rejected. There are no accepted elements.
3. *Indeterminate set* as $\hat{N} = (\emptyset, \emptyset, X)$. Here the idea is that we evaluate all elements but finally we do not feel able to say that some of them are true while the other are false.
4. *Indifferent set* as $\hat{0} = (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset)$. We evaluate nothing and of course we refuse to classify any elements.

As for the inclusion of two RIP-I sets, we can rediscover it using our union operator. Our aim is to say that $A \subseteq B$ if and only if $A \cup B = B$. That is, when $(A_T \cup B_T, A_F \cap B_F, X_A \cup X_B) = (B_T, B_F, X_B)$. This means that $A_T \subseteq B_T$, $B_F \subseteq A_F$ and $X_A \subseteq X_B$ (where the last three inclusions are understood in a classical sense). Clearly, we could obtain the same result starting from the assumption that $A \subseteq B$ if and only if $A \cap B = A$. Let us introduce the definition in a more official way.

Definition 3.6. Let X be a non-empty universe and assume that \mathcal{I} is an ideal on X . Suppose that A and B are two RIP-I sets on X . Then we say that A is *contained* in B (that is, $A \subseteq B$) if and only if $A_T \subseteq B_T$, $B_F \subseteq A_F$ and $X_A \subseteq X_B$.

One can easily check that this inclusion satisfies all the properties of partial order: it is reflexive, transitive and antisymmetric.

A natural question arises: what is the partial order of inclusion induced by \wedge ? Let us denote this order by \leq . Perhaps it is natural to assume that $A \leq B$ if and only if $A \wedge B = A$. It means that $A_T \cap B_T = A_T$, $A_F \cap B_F = A_F$ and $X_A \cup X_B = X_A$. Thus we obtain the following definition:

Definition 3.7. Let X be a non-empty universe and assume that \mathcal{I} is an ideal on X . Suppose that A and B are two RIP-I sets on X . Then we say that A is *strongly contained* in B (that is, $A \leq B$) if and only if $A_T \subseteq B_T$, $A_F \subseteq B_F$ and $X_B \subseteq X_A$.

Finally, we have the third option:

Definition 3.8. Let X be a non-empty universe and assume that \mathcal{I} is an ideal on X . Suppose that A and B are two RIP-I sets on X . Then we say that A is *strictly contained* in B (that is, $A \ll B$) if and only if $A_T \subseteq B_T$, $A_F \subseteq B_F$ and $X_A \subseteq X_B$.

Clearly, in the last case we have $A \ll B$ if and only if $A \Delta B = A$.

We defined basic logical (or set-theoretical) operators together with the most natural distinguished sets. Now we should think about the algebra of RIP-I sets.

4. Algebraic properties of standard operators

In this part of our paper we formulate and prove many properties of the operators introduced in the preceding section. First, let us concentrate on standard union and standard intersection (together with complement). Of course, many of the identities listed below are very natural.

Lemma 4.1. *Suppose that X is a non-empty universe equipped with some ideal \mathcal{I} . Let A , B and C be three RIP-I sets on X . Then the following properties are true:*

1. $A \cap B = B \cap A$ and $A \cup B = B \cup A$ (commutativity).

2. $A \cup (B \cup C) = (A \cup B) \cup C$ and $A \cap (B \cap C) = (A \cap B) \cap C$ (associativity).
3. $A \cup (A \cap B) = A$ and $A \cap (A \cup B) = A$ (absorption laws).
4. $A \cup (B \cap C) = (A \cup B) \cap (A \cup C)$ and $A \cap (B \cup C) = (A \cap B) \cup (A \cap C)$ (distributivity laws).
5. $(A \cup B)^c = A^c \cap B^c$ and $(A \cap B)^c = A^c \cup B^c$ (de Morgan laws).
6. $(A^c)^c = A$ (double negation law).

Proof. The proof is rather simple so we can omit the majority of details and leave it to the reader. Clearly, we should use commutativity, associativity, absorption and distributivity of classical union and intersection.

Think, for example, about de Morgan laws. We have $(A \cap B)^c = (A_T \cap B_T, A_F \cup B_F, X_A \cup X_B)^c = (A_F \cup B_F, A_T \cap B_T, X_A \cup X_B)$. But $A^c \cup B^c = (A_F, A_T, X_A) \cup (B_F, B_T, X_B) = (A_F \cup B_F, A_T \cap B_T, X_A \cup X_B)$, hence we obtain the same thing. \square

We can also prove that universal and empty RIP-I set have expected properties.

Lemma 4.2. *Suppose that X is a non-empty universe equipped with some ideal \mathcal{I} . Let A be an RIP-I set on X . Then the following properties are true:*

1. $(\hat{X})^c = \hat{\emptyset}$ and $(\hat{\emptyset})^c = \hat{X}$.
2. $A \cup \hat{X} = \hat{X}$ and $A \cap \hat{X} = A$.
3. $A \cup \hat{\emptyset} = A$ and $A \cap \hat{\emptyset} = A$.
4. $A \subseteq \hat{X}$ and $\hat{\emptyset} \subseteq A$.
5. $A \cap \hat{N} = (\emptyset, A_F, X)$, $A \cup \hat{N} = (A_T, \emptyset, X)$.
6. $A \cap \hat{0} = (\emptyset, A_F, X_A)$, $A \cup \hat{0} = (A_T, \emptyset, X_A)$.

Remark 4.1. *Our study allows us to say that for any $X \neq \emptyset$ and for any ideal \mathcal{I} on X , $(\mathfrak{P}_{RI}(X), \cap, \cup, ^c, \hat{\emptyset}, \hat{X})$ is an example of de Morgan algebra.*

In general, this algebra is not Boolean. Take $X = \{a, b, c, d, e, f, g\}$ together with $\mathcal{I} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Take $A = (\{a, b, d, e\}, \{a, b, c, f\}, \{a, b, c, d, e, f\})$. Then $A^c = (\{a, b, c, f\}, \{a, b, d, e\}, \{a, b, c, d, e, f\})$. Now:

1. $A \cup A^c = (\{a, b, c, d, e, f\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c, d, e, f\}) \neq (X, \emptyset, X) = \hat{X}$. Thus the law of the excluded middle does not hold.
2. $A \cap A^c = (\{a, b\}, \{a, b, c, d, e, f\}, \{a, b, c, d, e, f\}) \neq \hat{\emptyset}$. Thus the law of non-contradiction does not hold.

Note that if A is a P-I set then we always obtain $A \cup A^c = (A_T \cup A_F, \emptyset, X)$ and $A \cap A^c = (\emptyset, A_T \cap A_F, X)$.

Clearly, the fact that we have de Morgan algebra implies that we have a more general structure of lattice too.

Now let us introduce the following definition of set difference:

Definition 4.1. *Suppose that X is a non-empty universe with some ideal \mathcal{I} on it. Let A and B be two RIP-I sets. Then we define their *difference* as $A \setminus B = A \cap B^c$.*

In many ways, this difference behaves just like classical difference. But there are some non-classical aspects too.

Remark 4.2. *Let us think about the following identity: $A \setminus B = A \setminus (A \cap B)$. In classical setting we have: $A \setminus (A \cap B) = A \cap (A \cap B)^c = A \cap (A^c \cup B^c) = (A \cap A^c) \cup (A \cap B^c) = \emptyset \cup (A \cap B^c) = A \cap B^c = A \setminus B$. However, we know that in our setting $A \cap A^c$ is not necessarily empty (in RIP-I sense). Clearly, this observation is true for some other classes of non-classical sets (e.g. intuitionistic, intuitionistic fuzzy or just fuzzy).*

5. Algebraic properties of strong and strict intersection

In this subsection we would like to analyze certain properties of both strong and strict intersection. However, they will be studied together with standard operators of union and intersection. Thus, the mutual interplay of these connectives will be investigated too.

The first lemma in this subsection is somewhat trivial but it should be stated for the coherence of the whole theory. The proof can be omitted.

Lemma 5.1. *Let X be a non-empty universe with some ideal \mathcal{I} on it. Suppose that A , B and C are RIP-I sets on X . Then the following identities hold:*

1. $A \wedge B = B \wedge A$, $A \Delta B = B \Delta A$ (commutativity).
2. $A \wedge (B \wedge C) = (A \wedge B) \wedge C$, $A \Delta (B \Delta C) = (A \Delta B) \Delta C$ (associativity).
3. $A \wedge A = A \Delta A = A$ (idempotence).

The last lemma tells us that both $(\mathfrak{P}_{RI}(X), \wedge)$ and $(\mathfrak{P}_{RI}(X), \Delta)$ are semi-lattices (for any universe X).

The preorder induced by \wedge and Δ should be investigated in the context of universal, empty, indeterminate and indifferent set.

Lemma 5.2. *Assume that X is a non-empty universe and \mathcal{I} is an ideal on X . Let A be an RIP-I set on X . Then the following properties are true:*

1. $\hat{N} \leq A$.
2. $\hat{\emptyset} \ll A$.
3. $A \wedge \hat{X} = (A_T, \emptyset, X) = A \cup \hat{N}$.
4. $A \wedge \hat{\emptyset} = (\emptyset, A_F, X) = A \cap \hat{N}$.
5. $A \wedge \hat{N} = \hat{N}$.
6. $A \wedge \hat{\emptyset} = (\emptyset, \emptyset, X_A)$.
7. $A \Delta \hat{X} = (A_T, \emptyset, X_A) = A \cup \hat{\emptyset}$.
8. $A \Delta \hat{\emptyset} = (\emptyset, A_F, X_A) = A \cap \hat{\emptyset}$.
9. $A \Delta \hat{N} = (\emptyset, \emptyset, X_A) = A \wedge \hat{\emptyset}$.
10. $A \Delta \hat{\emptyset} = \hat{\emptyset}$.

Now we can say that both $(\mathfrak{P}_{RI}(X), \wedge, \hat{N})$ and $(\mathfrak{P}_{RI}(X), \Delta, \hat{0})$ are semi-lattices with zero (but without identity).

Now let us list down several identities that engage \wedge , \cup and \cap .

Lemma 5.3. *Suppose that X is a non-empty universe with some ideal \mathcal{I} . Let A , B and C be three RIP-I sets on X . Then the following properties of distributivity hold:*

1. $A \cup (B \wedge C) = (A \cup B) \wedge (A \cup C)$.
2. $A \wedge (B \cup C) = (A \wedge B) \cup (A \wedge C)$.
3. $A \wedge (B \cap C) = (A \wedge B) \cap (A \wedge C)$.
4. $A \cap (B \wedge C) = (A \cap B) \wedge (A \cap C)$.

Proof. 1. We have: $A \cup (B \wedge C) = A \cup (B_T \cap C_T, B_F \cap C_F, X_B \cup X_C) = (A_T \cup (B_T \cap C_T), A_F \cap (B_F \cap C_F), X_A \cup (X_B \cup X_C)) = ((A_T \cup B_T) \cap (A_T \cup C_T), A_F \cap B_F \cap C_F, X_A \cup X_B \cup X_C)$.

On the other hand, $(A \cup B) \wedge (A \cup C) = ((A_T \cup B_T) \cap (A_T \cup C_T), A_F \cap B_F \cap A_F \cap C_F, X_A \cup X_B \cup X_A \cup X_C) = ((A_T \cup B_T) \cap (A_T \cup C_T), A_F \cap B_F \cap C_F, X_A \cup X_B \cup X_C)$. We got the same expression.

2. We have $A \wedge (B \cup C) = A \wedge (B_T \cup C_T, B_F \cap C_F, X_A \cup X_B) = (A_T \cap (B_T \cup C_T), A_F \cap (B_F \cap C_F), X_A \cup X_B \cup X_C) = ((A_T \cap B_T) \cup (A_T \cap C_T), A_F \cap B_F \cap C_F, X_A \cup X_B \cup X_C)$.

On the other hand, $(A \wedge B) \cup (A \wedge C) = (A_T \cap B_T, A_F \cap B_F, X_A \cup X_B) \cup (A_T \cap C_T, A_F \cap C_F, X_A \cup X_C) = ((A_T \cap B_T) \cup (A_T \cap C_T), A_F \cap B_F \cap C_F, X_A \cup X_B \cup X_C)$. Again, the identity holds.

3. Similar to the previous case.
4. Similar to the first case.

□

The next lemma is similar.

Lemma 5.4. *Suppose that X is a non-empty universe with some ideal \mathcal{I} . Let A , B and C be three RIP-I sets on X . Then the following properties of distributivity hold:*

1. $A \cup (B \Delta C) = (A \cup B) \Delta (A \cup C)$.
2. $A \Delta (B \cup C) = (A \Delta B) \cup (A \Delta C)$.
3. $A \Delta (B \cap C) = (A \Delta B) \cap (A \Delta C)$.
4. $A \cap (B \Delta C) = (A \cap B) \Delta (A \cap C)$.

Proof. 1. On the left hand side we have: $A \cup (B \Delta C) = A \cup (B_T \cap C_T, B_F \cap C_F, X_B \cap X_C) = (A_T \cup (B_T \cap C_T), A_F \cap (B_F \cap C_F), X_A \cup (X_B \cap X_C)) = ((A_T \cup B_T) \cap (A_T \cup C_T), A_F \cap B_F \cap C_F, (X_A \cup X_B) \cap (X_A \cup X_C))$.

On the right hand side: $(A \cup B) \Delta (A \cup C) = (A_T \cup B_T, A_F \cap B_F, X_A \cup X_B) \Delta (A_T \cup C_T, A_F \cap C_F, X_A \cup X_C) = ((A_T \cup B_T) \cap (A_T \cup C_T), A_F \cap B_F \cap C_F, (X_A \cup X_B) \cap (X_A \cup X_C))$. Hence we obtain the same expression as on the left hand side.

2. On the left hand side: $A \Delta (B \cup C) = A \Delta (B_T \cup C_T, B_F \cap C_F, X_B \cup X_C) = (A_T \cap (B_T \cup C_T), A_F \cap (B_F \cap C_F), X_A \cap (X_B \cup X_C)) = ((A_T \cap B_T) \cup (A_T \cap C_T), A_F \cap B_F \cap C_F, (X_A \cap X_B) \cup (X_A \cap X_C))$.

Now on the right hand side: $(A \Delta B) \cup (A \Delta C) = (A_T \cap B_T, A_F \cap B_F, X_A \cap X_B) \cup (A_T \cap C_T, A_F \cap C_F, X_A \cap X_C) = ((A_T \cap B_T) \cup (A_T \cap C_T), A_F \cap B_F \cap C_F, (X_A \cap X_B) \cup (X_A \cap X_C))$. The same as on the left hand side.

3. Similar to the case above.
4. Similar to the first case.

□

As for the law of non-contradiction, let us think for a moment about $A \wedge A^c$. This will be $(A_T, A_F, X_A) \wedge (A_F, A_T, X_A) = (A_T \cap A_F, A_F \cap A_T, X_A \cup X_A) = (A_T \cap A_F, A_T \cap A_F, X_A)$. The first and the second component are identical but this is not a problem: note that by the very definition the intersection of A_T and A_F belongs to the ideal. Besides, we see that $A \wedge A^c = A \Delta A^c$. Of course the resulting set is not $\hat{\emptyset}$ (nor \hat{N} or $\hat{0}$).

5.1. A note on generalized operators

Generalized versions of our operators should be defined and analyzed too. In particular, they will be useful in possible topological considerations (where it is natural to speak about families closed e.g. on arbitrary unions or intersections; in the same way it is typical to define interior and closure by means of generalized unions and intersections).

Definition 5.1. Let $\{A_i : i \in J\}$ be an indexed family of ideal pseudo-intuitionistic sets on X , where J is some non-empty set. Then we define:

1. *Arbitrary standard union*: $\bigcup_{i \in J} A_i = (\bigcup A_T^i, \bigcap A_F^i, \bigcup X_A^i)$.
2. *Arbitrary standard intersection*: $\bigcap_{i \in J} A_i = (\bigcap A_T^i, \bigcup A_F^i, \bigcup X_A^i)$.
3. *Arbitrary strong intersection*: $\bigwedge_{i \in J} A_i = (\bigcap A_T^i, \bigcap A_F^i, \bigcup X_A^i)$.
4. *Arbitrary strict intersection*: $\Delta_{i \in J} A_i = (\bigcap A_T^i, \bigcap A_F^i, \bigcap X_A^i)$.

Remark 5.1. In particular, one can easily prove that if $\{A_i : i \in J\} \subseteq \{B_k : k \in K\}$, then $\bigcup_{i \in J} A_i \subseteq \bigcup_{k \in K} B_k$ and $\bigcap_{k \in K} B_k \subseteq \bigcap_{i \in J} A_i$. Of course the symbol " \subseteq " in the first part of the preceding sentence refers to classical inclusion of two families (consisting of non-classical, that is RIP-I, sets).

However, it is not necessarily true that $\bigwedge_{k \in K} B_k \subseteq \bigwedge_{i \in J} A_i$ nor that $\bigwedge_{i \in J} A_i \subseteq \bigwedge_{k \in K} B_k$.

Set $X = \{a, b, c, d, e, f\}$, let \mathcal{I} be $\{\emptyset\}$ and take $A = (\{a, b, c\}, \{d, e, f\}, X)$, $B = (\{a, b, d\}, \{c, e, f\}, X)$, $C = (\{a, c\}, \{b, e, f\}, X)$ and $D = (\{a, d\}, \{b, c, f\}, X)$. Let $\mathcal{S} = \{A, B\}$ and $\mathcal{T} = \{A, B, C, D\}$. Clearly, $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{T}$. Now, $\bigwedge \mathcal{S} = (\{a, b\}, \{e, f\})$, while $\bigwedge \mathcal{T} = (\{a\}, \{f\})$. However, $\bigwedge \mathcal{S}$ is not contained in $\bigwedge \mathcal{T}$ (because $\{a, b\}$ is not contained in $\{a\}$) and $\bigwedge \mathcal{T}$ is not contained in $\bigwedge \mathcal{S}$ (because $\{e, f\}$ is not contained in $\{e\}$).

However, the truth is that \wedge is associated rather with \leq than with \subseteq . One can prove that if $\{A_i : i \in J\} \subseteq \{B_k : k \in K\}$, then $\bigwedge_{k \in K} B_k \leq \bigwedge_{i \in J} A_i$. Moreover, in this situation $\Delta_{k \in K} B_k \ll \Delta_{i \in J} A_i$.

6. Conclusion and future work

Here we would like to stop. The aim of this paper is to introduce a general algebraic framework that will be used in our future considerations. Furthermore, we believe that the solutions presented in this article will be studied by other authors too. In particular, it would be good to define topological (or more general) structures using

RIP-I sets. We encourage the reader to analyze strong and strict intersection in the context of hypothetical closure-like operators. There are at least three aspects of our paper that generalize previous ideas. These are: the use of ideals, the use of relativized universe and the use of "non-standard" intersections.

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